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Microfibrillated cellulose as a new approach to develop lightweight cementitious composites: Rheological, Mechanical, and Microstructure Perspectives

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Abstract

Lightweight cementitious composites have a broad range of applications, such as filling or thermal insulation, and should display minimal mechanical properties. Our approach was to prepare mixtures of ordinary Portland cement (OPC) and micro- and nanofibrillated cellulose (CNF) at different water to cement ratios (W/C) to optimize a composite with low density, and either high compressive or flexural strength. The rheological data of W/C =1 CNF-OPC paste confirmed that the viscosity and yield stress of the sample containing 1.1 wt% cellulose fiber was abruptly increased in comparison to the sample without fibers. The results also confirmed the well miscibility (dispersion/distribution) of the OPC in high-water content (98 wt%) fiber medium due to absence of aggregation or agglomeration signatures in plotted rheological data. The dry densities of the CNF-OPC specimen were obviously reduced from 800 kg/m³ to 450 kg/m³ by increasing the content of fiber from 1.1 wt% (W/C=1) to 1.8 wt% (W/C = 4), respectively. However, the compressive strengths of the CNF-OPC mixtures were dramatically dropped at higher W/C. Based on the results of mechanical testing, the used lightening technique had less effect on flexural strength loss compared to that of compressive strength, which is related to the bridging action of micro- and nanofibrillated cellulose in the matrix.

Keywords: Micro- and nanofibrillated cellulose, cement, lightweight-composite, rheology.

Synopsis. Preparation of microfibrillated cellulose-ordinary Portland cement composites (CNF-OPC). CNF-OPC morphology, rheology and strength characterization.

1. Introduction

Today we are living in global warming crisis due to the emission of carbon dioxide, fossil fuel burning, and cement production. There is an essential need to decrease the volume of these sources to move toward zero carbon emission (1). Therefore, the use of bio-based materials such as cellulose can be directly or indirectly played an important role to decrease the global warming. The abundance of cellulosic materials such as wood, wood pulps and waste or by-products of industry (2) with annual production exceeding 1 trillion tons (3), along with their extraordinary physical, chemical (4), optical (5), and mechanical properties (6) in the nanoscale range, make cellulose and, in particular, cellulose nanofibers interesting for scientists and put them into the spotlight. Different descriptions of these nanoscale fibers are referred to in the literature: (i) cellulose nanowhiskers (CNW) or cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) are designated to represent short crystalline rod-like nanoparticles, while (ii) micro- and nanofibrillated cellulose (MFC) or (CNF) are termed to designate long flexible nanoparticles with either micro- or nanoscale fiber diameters, consisting of alternating crystalline and amorphous domains (7).

Novel processing methods are used to extract cellulose nanofibers by defibrillation of cellulose resources into different micro- and nanoscale morphologies. The so-called none-toxic micro- and nanofibrillated cellulose (CNF) gel-like products are mostly processed by grinding (8) (9) (10), homogenization/microfluidization (11) (12), and TEMPO-oxidation (13). The main issues of these methods are cost, very low fiber contents of around 2-5 wt% for CNF, hornification of the fibers as a result of drying of the gel, redispersion issues (e.g., for CNC) (14) and flocculation or aggregation of fibers within hydrophobic matrices, which affects the mechanical properties of the composites. However, the cost of CNF has been decreased due to market request and large-scale production. Moreover, the CNF gel with high water content has hydrophilic behavior which is caused by some dispersive and distributive barriers when they are compounded with a hydrophobic (bio)polymer (15). Twin-screw extrusion (TSE) as an alternative method has been recently used by scientists in the last decade to defibrillate cellulose fibers and to overcome the aforementioned solid content and cost issues (16) (17) (18) (19). However, poor dispersive and distributive mixing remains as a disadvantage of hydrophilic cellulose fibers (20).

The simple scenario of the cementitious or clay material is on the opposite side of the (bio)polymers extrusion process, as cement slurry consists of 25-50 wt% water. In other words,

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4 the disadvantage of CNF gel (high water content) can be grasped as an advantage and can be used
5 for preparing fiber-cement mixtures. Therefore, there is high potential to use bio-based materials,
6 such as CNF gel, which give rise to high-volume surface fiber networks that might improve the
7 flow behavior of the fiber-cement mixtures (fresh properties, rheology, resistance to bleeding),
8 density, crack resistance due to drying, and mechanical properties after processing and curing.
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14 There are several but not many works that show the beneficial effects of CNF when added as
15 reinforcement or as additive to cementitious matrices. Mejdoub et al. (21) reported enhanced
16 mechanical and thermal properties of CNF-cement systems compared to the control. Ardanuy et
17 al. (22) observed that the flexural strength of CNF-cementitious composites increases nearly two-
18 fold in comparison with cellulose-cement composites. Enhanced mechanical properties have also
19 been reported by Onuaguluchi et al. (23) when the CNF fibers were added to cement at 0.05-0.4%
20 additions. In another study the setting time and the degree of hydration of CNF-cement composite
21 increases with increasing proportions of CNF up to 0.2% (24). Improvements have also been
22 reported for the energy absorption property and wet/dry cycling durability of CNF-cement
23 composites (22) (23). The addition of CNF has been found to cause increase in yield stress of fresh
24 CNF-cement slurries, and the Vom Berg model provided the best fit for the shear rate-shear stress
25 flow curve (25) (26). Tang et al. (24) reported that the gel strength, yield stress and viscosity of
26 the CNF-cement increased due to the formation of an entangled fiber network. The same authors
27 reported that the quality of the used CNF alters the strength of the cement paste and changes in
28 rheological properties.
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43 Even though the amount of fiber content in CNF materials is very low (around 2-5 wt%), the CNF
44 gel shows a bulky behavior due to the high specific surface area of the fibers. Therefore, it can be
45 expected that the density of CNF-cement composites decreases and shows the behavior of
46 lightweight cement composites or foam concretes, wherein the air voids are entrapped into the
47 cementitious matrix and confined within the binding skeleton to drop the density of the matrix
48 during the setting and hardening stages (27). The advantages of light weight cement composites
49 can be reflected in the thermal and acoustic insulation properties, structural weight reduction, and
50 easy transportation and assemblage (28) (29). Different methods such as mechanical foaming (30)
51 (31) and chemical foaming techniques (32) (33) have been used to generate the air voids into the
52 cementitious matrix. However, other approaches such as alkali-activated materials have also been
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used to produce light weight cement-based composites due to their ecofriendly features (34). Therefore, bio-based CNF materials can be highlighted as an important alternative due to their beneficial effects on the sustainability, density, porosity, fresh property, rheological behavior, and mechanical properties of light weight fiber-cement composites.

In this work, microfibrillated cellulose (CNF) was produced and mixed with ordinary Portland cement (OPC) in different fiber proportions and water to cement ratios (W/C). The novel idea in this work is related to using the existing water in CNF gel, thus any extra water was not added to the composite mixtures. The primary goal of this work was aimed to tune the rheological changes of the mixtures due to different parameters such as shear rate and time evolution. The secondary goal was to prepare CNF-OPC composites with different fiber contents and W/C, to ultimately produce light weight cement composites with optimum mechanical properties. The microstructure of obtained CNF-OPC composites were studied to observe how the fibers and cement particles will be mixed and will affect the properties of CNF-cement composite.

2. Experimental plan

2.1. Materials and methods

Ordinary Portland cement 42.5R with specific chemical composition and physical properties (shown in **Table 1**) was used in this work. Never-dried softwood pulp as the raw source with a solid content of 36-37 wt% (Stora Enso, Oulu, Finland) and chemical composition of 2.45 wt% hemicellulose, 1.5 wt% lignin and 0.5 wt% inorganics (TAPPI-T 222 standard) was used to produce CNF.

Table 1 Chemical composition and physical properties of ordinary Portland cement 42.5R.

Physical properties		Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC-42.5R)										
		Chemical composition (%)										
Specific gravity	Specific surface (cm ² /g)	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	CaO	C ₃ S	C ₂ S	C ₃ A	C ₄ AF
3.11	300	21.1	4.37	3.88	1.56	0.52	0.39	63.33	51	22.7	5.1	11.9

The softwood pulp was soaked in water and processed by a Masuko super masscolloider MKCA6-2J (Japan) grinder. The Masuko grinder's stones were firstly closed in a tiny gap as long as the low friction zero gap to be confirmed. Then the soaked pulp slurry was poured into the grinder at a consistency of 2.3 wt%. The fiber slurry was passed three times through the grinder using a zero-

grinding stone gap; then, the stones were adjusted to negative gap values to fibrillate the pulp fibers. The process was repeated three times with -20 μm stone gap, three times with -40 μm stone gap, three times with -60 μm stone gap, and additional nine passes with -90 μm stone gap. The prepared CNF was mixed with OPC based on the samples' formulation (shown in **Table 2**) by a two-propeller mixer at a speed of 300 rpm for 10 minutes. The prepared samples were loaded in a mold or vane rheometer cup and vibrated for 1 minute. Two different molds ($50 \times 50 \times 50$) mm^3 and ($40 \times 40 \times 160$) mm^3 were used to measure density and mechanical properties after 28 days, respectively.

Table 2 Sample formulation and coding of material compositions and preparation methods.

Sample	CNF		OPC (wt%)	Total (wt%)	Water to cement ratio (W/C)
	Water (wt%)	Fiber (wt%)			
CNF*	97.7	2.3	0	100	N/A
W-C1	50	0	50	100	1
W-C1.5	60	0	40	100	1.5
W-C2**	66.7	0	33.3	100	2
WF-C1	49.4	1.1	49.4	100	1
WF-C1.5	59.3	1.3	39.4	100	1.5
WF-C2	66.5	1.5	32	100	2
WF-C3	73.8	1.7	24.5	100	3
WF-C4	78.7	1.8	19.5	100	4

* The sample was used for FE-SEM.

** The maximum W/C can be reached without fiber even with sedimentation.

2.2. Test procedures

2.2.1. Rheometry

The rheological measurements of cement paste and CNF-OPC mixtures were done using a TA Instrument Discovery HR-1 Hybrid Rheometer (New Castle, DE, USA). Different mixtures were prepared based on the prior formulations presented in **Table 2** to compare the flow behavior of the bulk cement paste without fibers against those of the CNF-OPC pastes. The rheological behavior of the samples under the strain-controlled mode was measured by vane rotor and grooved cup accessories. The steady state shear-viscosity, time sweep, and frequency sweep tests were done to investigate the rheological properties of bulk CNF-OPC mixtures at 23 °C. The wall-slip effect of the test protocol for the used medium was also checked at three different gaps (5000 ± 1000 μm), and the shear-viscosity data were regenerated at all gaps, confirming the absence of wall-slip. The reference gap of 5000 μm was fixed for all experiments, and the gap was slowly adjusted within 2

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4 minutes to erase additional stress and equilibrate the temperature between the sample and grooved
5 cup. The steady state shear-viscosity tests were done under a controlled shear rate in an ascending
6 and descending sequence of about 10 minutes (5 minutes for ramp-up then 5 minutes for ramp-
7 down) to show the flow behavior within the shear rate interval of 0.1 to 1000 s⁻¹ at 23 °C. The time
8 sweep tests were done under very low constant shear rate (0.1 s⁻¹) over 150 minutes to study the
9 hardening evolution of the mixtures. The linear regime of two samples was shortly checked via
10 strain sweep tests. Based on these results, a constant strain of 0.5% was used in the frequency
11 sweep tests, which were performed in the range of 0.1 to 100 rad.s⁻¹. The frequency sweep test
12 data was overlapped with steady state shear viscosity data to observe if the cement paste and CNF-
13 OPC composites will follow the Cox-Merz rule (35). The total preparation time for each sample
14 was recorded from the first contact of cement and water and included the subsequent steps of
15 mixing, vibrating, loading, and adjusting in grooved cup, and was controlled to be around 15 ± 0.2
16 minutes.
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31 The molded cement paste and CNF-OPC samples were tested under three-point bending (TPB)
32 load conditions by using the ASTM C78 recommendation (36). The flexural load was applied to
33 the beams at a displacement rate of 0.6 mm/min and a loading cell under 100 kN force. The flexural
34 load was recorded by using a Zwick, Z100 Roell testing machine (Ulm, Germany) and calculated
35 using the following equation:
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$$40 \quad \sigma_f = \frac{3FL}{2bh^2} \quad (1)$$

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44 where F is the total flexural load, L is span length (160 mm), b and h are width (40 mm) and height
45 (40 mm) of beams, respectively. The compressive strength was measured by using the ASTM
46 C349 recommendation for cube samples after having air dried for 28 days (37). The compressive
47 load was applied with a displacement rate of 1.8 mm/min. For each CNF-OPC sample, the flexural
48 and compressive strengths represent the average of the five measurements. Moreover, the dry
49 densities of CNF-OPC compositions were obtained by drying the cube samples (50 × 50 × 50)
50 mm³ at 105 ± 2 °C in an oven for 24 hours by using the ASTM C567 recommendation (38).
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4 FE-SEM-EDS: Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was used to study the chemical
5 characterization/elemental analysis of the samples. The sample is excited by an energy source and
6 dissipates some of the absorbed energy by ejecting a core-shell electron. A higher energy outer-
7 shell electron then proceeds to fill its place, releasing the difference in energy as an X-ray that has
8 a characteristic spectrum based on its atom of origin. The position of the peaks in the spectrum
9 identifies the element, whereas the intensity of the signal corresponds to the concentration of the
10 element. Compositional information, down to the atomic level, can be obtained with the addition
11 of an EDS detector to an electron microscope. As the electron probe is scanned across the sample,
12 characteristic X-rays are emitted and measured; each recorded EDS spectrum is mapped to a
13 specific position on the sample.
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23 FE-SEM: Field emission scanning electron microscopy (ZEISS ULTRA plus FE-SEM, Carl Zeiss
24 AG, Oberkochen, Germany) was used to study the microstructure of neat CNF and CNF-OPC
25 samples. The collected CNF-OPC mixtures were firstly dried at 100 ± 5 °C in an oven for 6 hours.
26 The samples were mounted on sample holders and platinum-coated before FE-SEM to avoid
27 charging. An acceleration voltage of 5 kV was used with the measurement distance of 6–8 mm.
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33 **3. Results and discussion**

34 3.1. Flow properties

35 3.1.1. Steady state mode rheology

36 The steady state ascending/descending shear-viscosity tests of the cement paste and CNF-OPC
37 were examined with equal W/C to understand the effect of CNF on the rheological behavior of the
38 mixtures. As shown in **Fig. 1a**, the ascending shear-viscosity plot of cement paste (W-C1) at low
39 shear rate interval (0.1 s^{-1}) was abruptly increased from 8 Pa.s to 4000 Pa.s when 1.1 wt% cellulose
40 nanofiber (WF-C1) was added to the mixture at a fixed W/C = 1. The flow properties of both
41 samples (W-C1 and WF-C1) are showing a shear thinning behavior and the viscosity trend of the
42 sample that contains CNF was greater – around 100x at intermediate and high shear rate intervals.
43 The increase of the viscosity can be related to the fiber-fiber entanglement and likely networks
44 between cement and nanofibers. The descending shear rate depicted a hysteresis for both samples
45 with equal W/C. However, the hysteresis at low shear rate for the sample with CNF was greater
46 than the sample without CNF, which is related to a competition between the fibers' network history
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and hardening of the cement matrix within 25 minutes. Moreover, any packing phenomenon or abrupt shear thickening behavior was not observed at low and intermediate interval confirming well dispersive mixing and absence of aggregation. With increase in fiber amount (WF-C2), the hysteresis of the ramp up and ramp down data at intermediate shear rates ($10\text{-}15\text{ s}^{-1}$) was decreased where the smooth plateau going to be formed. In contrast, the ramp up and ramp down data for the cement mixture (W-C2) showed greater hysteresis at intermediate shear rates due to the absence of fiber cement interactions. The observed difference can also be explained by the instability (bleeding) of the mixture without CNF. The rheological change was clearly pronounced the fiber-cement network while even at higher $W/C = 2$, the sample with 1.5 wt% cellulose nanofiber (WF-C2) showed a greater ascending/descending viscosity trend in comparison with cement paste at $W/C = 1$ (W-C1) (**Fig. 1a**). As the amount of cement in WF-C1 is greater than the amount of cement in WF-C2, the viscosity of WF-C1 at low shear rate interval (0.1 s^{-1}) remained two times higher than that of WF-C2. According to **Fig. 1a**, with increasing cellulose nanofiber content from 1.1 wt% (WF-C1) to 1.5 wt% (WF-C2), the rheological properties of CNF gel start to be more dominant than that of cement, as indicated by the so-called plateau of the curve at intermediate shear rate (15 s^{-1}); serving as a fingerprint of CNF rheological behavior (12).

Fig. 1. The comparison of flow behavior of cement paste and CNF-OPC mixtures at 23 °C.

a) shear versus viscosity plots, solid and open symbols indicate ascending (ramp up) and descending (ramp down) shear rate, respectively; b) shear rate versus stress.

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4 As shown in **Fig. 1b**, the alteration of yield stress for the cement paste and CNF-OPC with different
5 W/C was studied. The yield stress (τ_0) was defined as the peak of the shear versus stress curve
6 (39) at low shear rate interval ($0.1-1 \text{ s}^{-1}$), while the plastic viscosity (η_{pl}) can be computed as the
7 slope of a linear fit (40) at intermediate shear rate interval ($10-100 \text{ s}^{-1}$). The yield stress of CNF-
8 OPC composites with different W/C (or fiber proportion) were identified as around 927, 437, 400,
9 305, and 261 (Pa) for WF-C1, WFC1.5, WF-C2, WF-C3, and WF-C4 samples, respectively. The
10 mentioned peak can be defined for cement paste samples with W/C = 1 and 1.5 as around 1.9 and
11 1.1 (Pa), respectively. The comparison of plastic viscosity of W-C1 ($\eta_{pl} = 0.02 \text{ Pa.s}$) and WF-C1
12 ($\eta_{pl} = 6.79 \text{ Pa.s}$) is confirming the significant effect of the nanofibers on flow behavior. Based on
13 **Fig. 1b**, the increase in CNF from 1.1 to 1.5 wt% decreases the yield stress of the mixture as the
14 W/C was increased. However, the absence of CNF with equal W/C resulted in very low yield
15 stress. Therefore, it can be predicted to tune the greater yield stress using CNF in a lower W/C,
16 which is remarkable for processing applications such as 3D printing (39).
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30 The time-dependent response of the CNF-OPC composites at constant shear rate (0.1 s^{-1}) are
31 shown in **Fig. 2** to understand the stress evolution of the samples. At early ages (around 90
32 seconds), the stress and viscosity trends of all CNF-OPC samples were increased due to the
33 increase of the strain imposed by the test conditions until a peak value or a plateau is reached (**Fig.**
34 **2a**). In this phase, the material behaves as an elastic solid. The time at which the plateau or the
35 peak is reached is almost the same, meaning that the critical strain does not depend on W/C. At
36 later age, the shear stress of WF-C1 was decreased to reach an equilibrium value (at around 2500-
37 8000 seconds) which is the signature of an unstructured flowing material. This response is
38 obviously different from the neat cement paste with W/C = 1, whereas the stress increases was
39 observed due to hardening and also reported in other works (41). This difference can be attributed
40 to the retarding effect brought by the CNF. However, the shear thinning behavior of the other
41 samples with greater W/C continued to decrease and the mentioned equilibrium occurred within
42 the time frame of 6000-7000 seconds, where the hydration effect and structural build-up of cement
43 is only happening at these times.
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56 The fluctuation of stress data and the saw-tooth response can be related to breakdown/recovery of
57 the fiber-fiber entanglements, fiber-cement networks, and interparticle forces of the mixtures (**Fig.**
58 **2b**). However, the same behaviors such as the initial shear thinning and saw-tooth response have
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4 been reported as microstructural breakdown in the material under applied shear rate (41). In brief,
5 the CNF-OPC composite with $W/C = 1$ showed the highest yield stress among the samples and the
6 normalized time-dependent stress remained constant (350-400 Pa) during the time window of
7 2500-8000 seconds. However, the stress values increased after 8000 seconds confirming the
8 chemical reaction of the composite and hardening of the mixture. At higher $W/C = 2, 3,$ and $4,$ it
9 was obvious that the mentioned linear stress equilibrium occurred at later time and the hardening
10 fingerprint was not observed in the experimental time window. Interestingly, at $W/C = 1.5$ the
11 composites did not reach the linear equilibrium, which can be related to intermolecular competition
12 between the CNF gel and cement particles to dominate their rheological properties. It could be
13 interesting to add setting accelerator to obtain a faster hardening of the CNF added materials close
14 to the one can be observed by neat cement at low W/C .

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46 **Fig. 2.** The evolution of stress as function of time in constant applied shear rate of 0.1 s^{-1} at
47 $23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. a) the resolution of the first 200 seconds, b) overall testing time of 9000 seconds.

48 3.1.2. Dynamic mode rheology

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51 The dynamic properties of CNF-OPC

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54 The dynamic rheology of CNF-OPC composites was measured as a function of frequency at a
55 constant strain of 0.5%, which is significant for processing applications such as extrusion. As
56 shown in **Fig. 3a**, the dynamic behavior of all CNF-OPC composites with different W/C showed
57 a solid-like behavior as the storage modulus (G') was higher than the loss modulus (G'').
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Furthermore, any cross-over between (G') and (G'') for the CNF-OPC composites was not observed and the solid-like component of the mixtures (G') were smoothly increased with increment of frequency. At low frequency the composite with $W/C = 1$ had a higher (G') value in comparison with other samples. However, the (G') for the sample with $W/C = 1.5$ and 2 were close within the whole frequency interval. Such result is in agreement with the high yield stress of the samples with CNF.

Fig. 3. The steady-state and dynamic rheology of CNF-OPC composites with different W/C at 23 °C. a) frequency sweep test, b) comparison of steady state rheology (solid symbols) and dynamic rheology (open symbols) due to Cox-Merz rule.

Due to the Cox-Merz rule, the complex viscosity data $|\eta^*(\omega)|$ from dynamic testing can be overlapped with the shear viscosity data $\eta(\dot{\gamma})$ from steady state testing at low shear rates and frequencies (35). In general, this principle is used for molten polymers or highly dense particle mediums, which is remarkable for extrusion processing. However, it is interesting to study the cement-based materials response with the so-called Cox-Merz principle, which can be related to extrusion or 3D printing applications. As shown in **Fig. 3b**, the plotted data of CNF-OPC composites at $|\eta^*(\omega)| = \eta(\dot{\gamma})$ does not show any overlapping of steady state and dynamic data. However, the shear viscosity and complex viscosity of the CNF-OPC composite with low $W/C = 1$ are close at low shear rate or frequency. It can be assumed that with decrement of W/C the fiber-cement mixture shows more dense properties and the mentioned rule can be applied for cement-based materials. However, the main reasons for the steady state and dynamic data deviations might

be related to the presence of intra- and inter-molecular hydrogen bonds or the negative charges of the cellulose nanofiber particles in the cement matrix.

3.2. Dry density

One of the main important indices to assess lightweight cementitious compositions is dry density. Lighter material reflects higher porosity, although this does not reflect the pore structure (size and distribution of pores) of the matrix. As the dry density of the used OPC without CNF (W/C = 1) is 1480 kg/m³, **Fig. 4a** shows the influence of adding CNF to the cementitious pastes. Dry densities of the mixtures were consistently reduced from 800 kg/m³ to 450 kg/m³ by increasing the content of CNF from 1.1 to 1.8, respectively. In order to obtain a lightweight construction material, the dry density should be lower than 1000 kg/m³, and all developed materials in this study meet this important requirement. Additionally, as shown in **Fig. 4b**, a nonlinear correlation was developed between density and W/C with a high coefficient of determination ($R^2 \geq 0.96$).

Fig. 4. a) Dry density of the mixtures containing different contents of CNF, b) correlation between density and water to cement ratio.

3.3. Compressive and flexural strength

Lightening the cementitious materials degrades the mechanical strength of the lightweight composites due to the porous structure of the material, where this strength loss mainly depends on the lightening technique. Evaporation of free water from cementitious compositions, once set, results in an increase in porosity of the matrix, as free water does not participate in chemical reactions and so its evaporation leaves voids. Evaporation of high amount of free water results in

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4 forming a porous structure in the matrix. The water evaporation process in mixtures containing
5 CNF has some aspects, including: i) the presence of pulp fibers in CNF provides multiple air
6 channels in the cementitious matrix, which facilitates the removal process of free water from the
7 matrix, and the formation of pores in the matrix; ii) the presence of CNF provides a physical
8 confinement system in the cementitious matrix and, this confinement leads to slowed evaporation
9 of water from the cementitious matrix; iii) good interaction of pulp fibers with water during the
10 preparation process of CNF submits new constrains for slowed evaporation of free water. The first
11 mechanism results in air entering the matrix and generating fine pores within the matrix, while the
12 second and third mechanisms reduces the rate of free water evaporation from the matrix at the
13 early ages of casting. The first mechanism can be effective in obtaining a lightweight material with
14 a high number of fine pores. Additionally, the slowed water evaporation leads to convert a weak
15 amount of remaining free water into gel water at the early age of casting, which prolonged
16 significantly the setting time of these lightweight materials. This prolongation makes them
17 completely appropriate for casting in real applications.
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31 **Fig. 5** indicates the influence of adding different contents of CNF on the mechanical strength of
32 the cementitious compositions. Increasing CNF to cement ratio (and therefore W/C) forms more
33 fine pores, and degrades the mechanical strength compared to the mixtures containing lower
34 amounts of CNF (and lower W/C). As expected, both compressive and flexural strength
35 consistently decreased with increasing amount of CNF and W/C so that the compressive strength
36 varied from 7.5-1 MPa for mixtures containing CNF 1.1-1.8 %, respectively, as shown in **Fig. 5a**.
37 Furthermore, the flexural strength changed from 3.6-1 MPa for mixtures containing CNF 1-4,
38 respectively. Comparing the developed strength for the lightweight materials with their reference
39 cementitious pastes in **Fig. 5b** revealed that the used lightening technique has less effect on flexural
40 strength loss compared to that of compressive strength. This is due to the bridging action of micro-
41 and nanofibrillated cellulose in the matrix. It was also visually observed that the presence of CNF
42 (regardless of its content) had a significant impact on mitigating drying shrinkage to prevent
43 cracking. The plain cementitious compositions with W/C higher than two exhibited significant
44 shrinkage, which resulted in cracks formed on their surfaces. Therefore, measuring the mechanical
45 strength for the plain cementitious compositions with W/C higher than 2 was not possible.
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Fig. 5. a) Mechanical strength for mixtures containing different contents of CNF, b) mechanical strength of mixtures containing different contents of CNF to mechanical strength of the reference mixtures without CNF, c) compressive strength to density ratio of mixtures containing different contents of CNF, d) comparison of the compressive strength versus density for different foamed concrete and this work (42) (43) (44) (45) (46).

For lightweight construction materials with density lower than 1000 kg/m^3 , the compressive strength to density ratio varies between $0.5\text{-}14 \times 10^{-3} \text{ MPa.m}^3/\text{kg}$ (42) (43). Higher values of this ratio means that the material has higher strength with lower density, which is appropriate for lightweight materials. According to the obtained results in **Fig. 5c**, the compressive strength to density ratio for developed materials through using this lightening technique varied between $2\text{-}9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ MPa.m}^3/\text{kg}$, which is an acceptable interval. The compressive strength versus density for different lightweight cementitious materials is shown in **Fig. 5d**. Based on the recorded data, the

compressive strength of OPC-based foam concretes is in the range of 0.25–13 MPa for densities in the range of 200–1400 kg/m³ (44) (45). The compressive strength could have either linear or nonlinear correlation with density.

Accordingly, the compressive strength of the materials developed in this study have a nonlinear correlation with density, and the compressive strength increases with a steep slope beyond a density of 800 kg/m³. The nonlinear correlation between compressive strength and density in this study is more related to W/C (cement content) and bulk networks of CNF gel. It can be interpreted from the data (star symbols in **Fig. 5d**) that the W/C = 1 is a threshold ratio for the CNF-OPC where the composite has a density lower than 800 kg/m³ with an optimum compressive strength of 7.4 MPa. Therefore, at the same W/C and without CNF, the density (1480 kg/m³) and the compressive strength (13 MPa) will be dropped with presence of the fiber networks by 48% and 42% respectively. Increasing of the W/C from 1 to 2 is also caused the decrement of density and compressive strength by 10 % and 55% respectively. In one hand the fiber networks caused the decrement of the density but on the other hand it decreased the compressive strength. In brief, the abrupt decrement of density is occurred at W/C = 1 when the fiber networks are involved and the dramatic strength loss is occurred at W/C = 2 when the fiber networks are increased and cement content decreased. This is a very promising result for this lightening technique, showing the potential to reach high mechanical strengths at densities above 800 kg/m³ and within 1000 kg/m³.

3.4. Microstructural and EDS analysis

The FE-SEM images of CNF and CNF-OPC mixtures at different W/C are presented in **Fig. 6**, and they support the findings of the rheological and mechanical investigations. As shown in **Fig. 6a**, the bulk network of microfibrillated cellulose confirmed the high porosity gel with well-distributed voids (1-3 μm) and high aspect ratio fibers (width 100-500 nm and length 5-10 μm). The mentioned networks increased the rheological properties of the CNF-OPC mixtures and decreased the density of the composites. As shown in **Fig. 6b**, some large cement flocs (showed in circle line) were formed with equal W/C and lowest CNF content. While with the increment of CNF proportion in composites, the fiber networks were controlled the forming of large cement flocs or high dense composites (**Fig. 6c-6f**). Based on the mechanical/density results in **Fig. 5d** and micrograph observation **Fig. 6a-6b**, the bulk density of CNF gel is caused the lower density of the composite due to fiber networks. However, the cement ratio was sufficient to form the

coherence connection of the large flocs in CNF-OPC composite and to reach the optimum compressive strength. Unlike, increasing of W/C from 1 to 2 (or decreasing of cement ratio) caused the large flocs turn to smaller flocs and the mixture shifted to form a bulk cement composite. These results are in agreement with 25 % of the density decrement and 62 % of dramatic compressive strength loss due to decreasing of cement ratio (**Fig. 5d** and **Fig. 6d**). Moreover, increasing of W/C ratio (or CNF content) the composite is caused to form highly porous structure as the CNF networks are more dominant in CNF-OPC mixture than cement ratio, which is in agreement of plateau in rheological data. It is remarkable to mention that the large flocs as shown in **Fig. 6b** can be observed as fluctuation or bump at high shear rate interval for steady state rheology shown in **Fig. 1a**. Therefore, the increment of W/C and in follow the fiber content works as barrier to form the large flocs and result in a uniform mixture. Based on the FE- SEM observations, it seems that the CNF networks can be applied as sort of nuclei and the cement matrix forming the composite through the fibers' network. Noteworthy is that the increment of CNF content decreases the density and increases the microcracks in composite, which is the main reason for strength loss (47).

Fig. 6. FE-SEM images of CNF and mixture of CNF-OPC. a) CNF, b) CNF-OPC at W/C=1, c) CNF-OPC at W/C=1.5, d) CNF-OPC at W/C=2, e) CNF-OPC at W/C=3, f) CNF-OPC at W/C=4 (**Table 2**).

A chemical analysis of the air-dried CNF-OPC composite was also performed to observe any possible chemical reactions or critical changes between the main elements of cement and cellulose nanofibers (**Fig. 7** and **Table 3**).

Fig.7. The EDS mapping spectrum of CNF-OPC (W/C = 1). Scale bar is 10 μ m.

Table 3 The EDX spectrum for the CNF-OPC (W/C =1).

		Spectrum																							
Label		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
Na		2,92	2,11	-	3,79	3,5	3,63	1,74	-	-	2,47	3,72	0,9	1,06	3,04	1,84	3,32	3,22	2,25	0,83	-	1,22	2,05	2,88	-
Mg		3,19	1,95	-	5,34	4,21	2,65	2,48	-	-	3,65	3,88	0,83	-	2	2,57	5,44	1,72	1,25	-	-	1,32	1,6	6,27	-
Al		3,91	2,92	-	5,85	5,62	6,54	1,55	3,19	-	4,49	6,93	1,61	-	4,95	2,3	6,58	6,72	5,81	1,13	-	-	4,85	6,11	-
Si		29,5	19,95	1,63	38,08	35,72	43,59	13,36	22,02	5,92	40,06	53,5	16,78	8,44	38,25	14,14	44,73	50,17	48,92	8,41	5,6	8,73	42,37	44,99	3,42
K		2,64	1,24	-	3,05	2,84	3,48	1,05	1,22	-	3,46	3,88	3,43	-	4,01	1,23	3,47	3,69	5,63	1,32	-	0,9	4,74	4,39	3,97
Ca		54,36	71,83	98,37	37,83	46,01	36,62	79,82	70,73	94,08	42,23	23,69	73,52	90,5	44,24	76,13	31,76	30,7	31,86	88,3	94,4	87,83	39,41	30,37	92,61
Fe		3,48	-	-	6,06	2,09	3,49	-	2,84	-	3,64	4,39	2,93	-	3,5	1,79	4,71	3,79	4,27	-	-	-	4,98	4,98	-
Total		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

In this regard, the EDX spectrums were monitored for the sample with an equal proportion of water and cement (W/C = 1) to observe the probable changes in the samples, as shown in **Fig. 7** and **Table 3**. In one hand, the main chemical bonds of cellulose contain carbon, hydrogen and oxygen and on the other hand, the main chemical bonds of cement paste contain calcium, silica and hydrogen (C-S-H). As there is not any calcium and silica in the CNF gel, CNF can affect C-S-H

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4 gel thorough their hydrogen bonds. EDS analysis showed that the main chemical components of
5 the CNF-OPC mixture is related to calcium (average 61.13%) and silica (average 26.59%), which
6 are the main components can significantly alter the strength. Moreover, EDS analysis can elucidate
7 that the mineral chemical component of the mixture hydrogen bonds in C-S-H can be affected by
8 either water or the hydrogen bonds of CNF. The topography images (FE-SEM) confirmed that the
9 quality of C-S-H gels did not change significantly. As the content of CNF compare to cement-
10 water is low, therefore the amount of hydrogen supplied be CNF will be low. It is noteworthy to
11 mention that the low amount of CNF (less than 0.5 wt%) will increase the degree of hydration and
12 compressive strength of the CNF-OPC composite (47). Therefore, the 1 wt% CNF content (in this
13 work) did not increase the degree of hydration and strength, which has been already confirmed by
14 rheological and mechanical data. Accordingly, it was observed that cellulose fibers had no
15 significant contribution in forming calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) as the main product of the
16 hydration of OPC and primarily responsible for the strength gaining. However, degree of
17 hydration, durability and crystallinity of such system (CNF-OPC) needs to be studied in further
18 study.
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32 **4. Conclusions**

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35 In this study, the preparation of super lightweight cementitious composite with eco-friendly
36 cellulose nanofibers was investigated. Based on rheological and morphological results, the CNF
37 gel and OPC were well dispersed/distributed as no flow fluctuation can be observed at low and
38 intermediate shear rates, and this was confirmed by micrograph observations. The mixture of CNF
39 gel and OPC resulted in an abrupt increase in yield stress and viscosity, which can be attributed to
40 cellulose networks and good distribution/dispersion of cement within the CNF-gel-voids. The
41 mentioned voids played a key role in keeping the cement particles and further decreasing the dry
42 density of the composite, which was reduced from 800 to 450 kg/m³ with increasing W/C from 1
43 to 4, respectively. In general, the use of CNF gel degraded the mechanical strength, where the loss
44 of compressive strength was greater than that of flexural strength in comparison with the reference
45 sample at equal W/C due to the bridging action of micro- and nanofibrillated cellulose in the
46 matrix. With a dry density within the interval of 450-800 kg/m³, a compressive strength of 7.5-1
47 MPa, and a flexural strength of 3.6-1 MPa, the developed CNF-OPC lightweight composites are
48 adequate for use as construction building materials for lightweight applications. Additionally,
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4 using CNF-gel significantly controlled the drying shrinkage of the composites at all W/Cs as
5 visually observed. Microstructural analysis of the cementitious compositions also revealed that
6 cellulose fibers had no major contribution in forming the hydration products of OPC.
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